

IDENTIFYING KEY COMPONENTS FOR LAW OF EVIDENCE SUBJECT AND THE NEED TO UPDATE THE EXISTING SYLLABUS

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Abstract

At the end of every court cases whether in civil or criminal, one important question will be asked namely whether the parties to the legal proceeding would be able to prove their case based on the quantum of proof provided by the law. Quantum of proof refers to the amount or level of proof needed in legal proceedings to prove or disprove a fact. It is closely related to the concept of the burden of proof, which specifies which party is responsible for providing sufficient evidence to meet the required quantum or standard of proof. The quantum of proof defines how much evidence is needed to prove something in court. It sets the threshold that must be met to prove a fact. Common standards of proof include: Firstly, preponderance of evidence or more likely than not. Secondly, beyond a reasonable doubt or virtually certain. The level required depends on the type of case. Civil cases generally require lower quantum's of proof than criminal cases. All these points are very important to be address to the students who are undertaking law degree in the school of law. Every school of law should have prepared comprehensive law subjects course outline to be taught to their law students. Among all the law subject, law of evidence subject is seen as important law subject as it addresses the issue surrounding the submission of evidence. The submission of evidence is very important for all cases whether it is civil or criminal cases. Without evidence, a party to a litigation cannot prove their legal dispute thus making their legal submission in the court of law futile. Thus, it is very important for the law of evidence subject course outline included every aspect over the process on the submission of evidence in order for the students to fully understand about the law of evidence itself and master the art over submission of evidence. Before preparing a comprehensive law of evidence course outline, it is important for the instructor to the subject to identify all the important key components to the law of evidence subject. Without having all the necessary key components to the law of evidence subject, it will make the course outline weak thus affect the teaching and learning process. It is the object of this paper to identify the key components for law of evidence subject. In Malaysia, the submission of evidence is heavily regulated by the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56], as such, this paper will analyse the issue based on the existing legislation in the country. It is very important for the existing course outline on the subject inserted all the essential components for law of evidence. This is to ensure students have the basic idea about law of evidence subject and would able to use their knowledge during practice.

Keywords: Evidence, key, component

1. INTRODUCTION

The role of evidence is very important for all court cases. Whether the legal battle take place in civil or criminal court, the submission of evidence is highly vital in order for the court to arrive to their final conclusion. (Dr Claudia Lau and Dr Tan Swee Kiow, 2020). In law, evidence refers to any information whether it is in the form of documents, oral testimony, physical, circumstantial or others that the plaintiff, defendant, prosecutor or accused presents to the court in order for the court to rule in his or her favor. Crucial to remember, all over the world, one of the most sacred principles in any legal system holding that a defendant or accused is innocent until been proven guilty by the court of the competent jurisdiction. In other words, the prosecutor or anyone who bring the legal action must prove their case against the defendant or accused according to existing all rules and procedures based on the standard or quantum of proof. Basically, there are two sets of standard or quantum of proof which need to be satisfied before the defendant or accused can be found guilty and faced legal sentence namely balance of probabilities which been adopted in civil trial and beyond a reasonable doubt for criminal trial. Reference can be made to the local case of *Sinnaiyah & Sons Sdn Bhd v Damai Setia Sdn Bhd* [2015] 5 MLJ on this point. Until the case properly been proven and final judgement is delivered by the court of competent jurisdiction, it must be known that one is considered innocent unless proven otherwise. Thus, the submission of evidence is very vital to build a case in the court. Absence of evidence can essentially put an end to a person's legal claim. Evidence can take many forms and it helps the judge determine that one or the other party has proven the elements of his or her case. If one party does not have evidence to back up the things he or she said in the court, then the court must not side in his or her favor. The need for evidence is part and parcel to uphold justice and to do fairness toward everyone. The submission of evidence is needed to establish the truth of the allegation put forward in a legal case. (A.K. Sarkar and S.K. Awasthi, 1996, pp: 160 – 161). The requirement to have strong evidence to support any particular case not only arise due to ensure justice and fairness in any court proceeding, but also because of common sense and logic. (Haswira Nor Mohamad Hashim and Anida Mahmood, 2009, pp: 98 – 121). To the end, court decisions are to be based on truth founded on evidence, a primary duty of courts is to conduct proper proceedings so as to hear and consider every piece of evidence which been submitted by the parties to the proceeding. The so-called law of evidence is made up largely of procedural regulations concerning the proof and presentation of facts, whether involving the testimony of witnesses, the presentation of documents or physical objects, or the assertion of a foreign or international law. The many rules of evidence that have evolved under different legal systems have, in the main, been founded on experience and shaped by varying legal requirements of what constitutes admissible and sufficient proof. (Britannica, 2024).

The important of justice and fairness has also been highlighted in Islamic legal system as well. There have been many verses in the Holy Qur'an as well as the saying of the Holy Prophet Muhammad SAW which emphasis on the important of justice and fairness in daily aspect of life including when settling any dispute between parties. For example, Allah SWT said in the Holy Qur'an "Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due and when you judge between people to judge with justice. Excellent is that which Allah instructs you. Indeed, Allah is ever Hearing and Seeing" (Surah An – Nisa: 58). The Holy Prophet Muhammad SAW himself has carried out many actions in line with the principle of justice and value. There have been many cases which been reported where the Holy Prophet Muhammad SAW decided cases based on merit with justice and equity, irrespective of people color, creed, race or gender. The Holy Prophet Muhammad SAW also has instructed others and those close to him to uphold justice, fairness and to prevent violent and oppression. From a report by Abu Daud "Ali RA said: The Prophet SAW had sent me to Yemen as a judge. I said to the Prophet SAW, O Prophet, why do you send me while I'm still young and ignorant on matters of judiciary? The Prophet SAW said verily Allah will grant His guidance on your heart and will strengthen your tongue. If two men came arguing before you, do not give judgment until you have heard the argument of the second man as you have heard the argument of the first, this is more fitting for you so that the matter would be clear to you when your give your judgment". Ali RA said, since then I have never had any doubts while giving judgment". (Mahmud Saedon A. Othman, 2000, pp. 1 – 14 and Afzalur Rahman, 1995, pp: 347 – 356). Important to know, injustice, discrimination, favoritism, partiality and double standard practices have no place in Islam. (Dr Muhammad Hisyam Bin Mohamad, 2021). In order to ensure fairness prevails in human life, Islam recognizes the concept of *al-'adl* (justice) and *al-ihsan* (benevolence). In Surah al-Nahl: 90 Allah SWT asserts to the effect: "Surely Allah enjoins the doing of justice and the doing of good (to others) and the giving to the kindred, and He forbids indecency and evil and rebellion; He admonishes you that you may be mindful". Hence the concept of justice should become the fundamental guiding principle of all human activities and this include in the process to seek justice through legal means in court. Among the

way to achieve justice in court is through submission of evidence to support or deny any allegations. Without evidence, it will be very difficult to uphold justice and give the right to the rightful people.

2. LAW OF EVIDENCE IN MALAYSIA

The law of Malaysia is mainly based on the common law legal system. This was a direct result of the colonisation of Malaya (Peninsular Malaysia), Sarawak, and North Borneo (Now Sabah) by Britain between the early 19th century to the 1960s. (Wu Min Aun, 1997, pp: 1 – 41). The supreme law of the land is the Federal Constitution. As the highest law in the country, the Federal Constitution sets out the legal framework and rights of Malaysian citizens. There are basically three sources of Malaysian law namely written law, unwritten law and Muslim law. (Lee Mei Pheng, 1997, pp: 13 – 47). There are several laws which operates in the country. Federal laws enacted by the Parliament of Malaysia apply throughout the country. There are also state laws enacted by the State Legislative Assemblies which applies in the particular state. The Federal Constitution also provides for a unique dual justice system namely the man-made laws (criminal and civil) and Syariah laws. Due to these unique dual justice systems, the county also has two set of judicial avenues namely the Civil Court and the Syariah Court Unlike Saudi Arabia which effectively equates Syariah law to national law, Malaysia only partially implements the system. Syariah law in Malaysia applies only to restricted areas of personal and family law, such as marriage and custody-and only to Muslims. Article 121 (1A) of the Federal Constitution gives exclusive jurisdiction to the Syariah Courts in the administration of Islamic laws. (Ashgar Ali Ali Mohamed (Ed.), 2014, pp: 319 – 349). However, despite having Islam as its official religion, Malaysia is not strictly an Islamic state as it allows other religions to be practiced within it in peace and harmony. Most of the Malaysian law is a man-made or secular civil law derived from the British common law system. Often, English legislation and case law still apply, as legacies of colonialism that remain in many former British colonies. (Victoria Soh, 2020). The application of English law or common law is specified in statutes. Section 5 of Criminal Procedure Code [Act 593] states that English law shall be applied in cases where no specific legislation has been enacted. Similarly, in context of civil law, Sections 3 and 5 of Civil Law Act [Act 67] allows for application of English common law, equity rules, and statutes in Malaysian civil cases where no specific laws have been made.

The effect of having these unique dual justice systems can also be seen in the evidence matter. As for civil court, the submission of evidence is regulated under the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. Section 2 of Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] states that “This Act shall apply to all judicial proceedings in or before any court, but not to affidavits presented to any court or officers, nor to proceedings before an arbitrator”. This means that Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] regulates the submission of evidence for civil and criminal proceeding in the country. Reference can be made to the following case of *Saminathan v PP* [1955] MLJ 121, *Re Loh Kah Kheng* (1990) 2 MLJ 126, *Malaysia Building Society Bhd v Univein Sdn Bhd* [2003] 5 MLJ 394, *Far East Holdings Bhd & Anor v Majlis Ugama Islam and Adat Resam Melayu Pahang and other appeals* [2018] 1 MLJ 1 and many more. The word “court” under Section 2 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] means a court established by or under Part IX of the Federal Constitution which includes a judge, a Sessions Court judge, a Magistrate, and every person legally authorized to take evidence (Except for arbitrator). Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] does not apply to Domestic Inquiry, Tribunals, Industrial Court and Syariah Court. Examples of Tribunals include Tribunal for Consumer Claims, Tribunal for Homebuyers Claims, and Copyright Tribunal. The exclusion of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] from the Syariah Court can also be seen under Section 131 of the Syariah Court Evidence Act (FT) 1997 [Act 561] which clearly states “With the coming into operation of this Act (i.e The Syariah Court Evidence Act), the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] shall not be applicable to the Court. (i.e. Syariah Court)”. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is modeled and based on the Indian Evidence Act of 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872] drafted by Sir James Stephen. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is modeled on the Indian Evidence Act which is a codified form of English Law. Per Thomson CJ (as he then was) in *Looi Wooi Saik v PP* [1962] MLJ 337, 339 (CA) stated “In this country the question is governed by the terms of the Evidence Ordinance which is the same as the Indian Evidence Act...It is generally accepted that the Indian Act was drafted by Sir James Stephen in 1872 with the intention of stating in a codified form of English law relating to evidence as it stood at that date”. The Indian Evidence Act 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872] which also is based on the English law of evidence in the late 19TH century with certain modifications, which were made to suit the local circumstances in India. As result of several amendments, the local Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] has certain provisions which are not found in the Indian Evidence Act 1872 [Act No. 1 of 1872]. The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] has 167 sections which covered various aspect over submission of evidence in the Malaysian court. Generally, the Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] embodied aspects over the definition of evidence, types of evidence and the

method of authentication of evidence. (Augustine Paul, 2000, pp. 1 – 13).

3. KEY COMPONENTS FOR LAW OF EVIDENCE

Though the Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] embodied 167 sections, there are several key components in it which is essential for us to understand the operation of law of evidence in Malaysia. These includes the definition of evidence, the idea over relevancy, the concept of best evidence rule as well as burden and standard of proof. These essential components should be included in the course outline for law of evidence subject and be discuss with the students in the classroom in detail. All these essential components will be discussed separated below.

3.1 Definition of Evidence

In its broadest definition, the term evidence refers to anything that is presented to prove something else is true or exists. In the legal system, evidence is any type of proof presented at trial, for the purpose of convincing the judge and/or jury that alleged facts of the case are true. This may include anything from witness testimony to documents, and objects, to photographs. The law provides specific rules of evidence which govern what may and may not be presented at trial. (Legal Dictionary, 2015). The definition of evidence has been provided under the Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56]. Section 3 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] states “evidence” includes (a) all statements which the court permits or requires to be made before it by witnesses in relation to matters of fact under inquiry: such statements are called oral evidence; (b) all documents produced for the inspection of the court: such documents are called documentary evidence”. Sharma J in the case of *PP v Sanassi* [1970] 2 MLJ 198, 200-201 (HC) “It was urged upon me by the learned deputy public prosecutor that because the words “permits or requires” appears in the definition of evidence in the Evidence Ordinance, anything which the Court permits the witness to say constitutes evidence. I am of the view that that construction on those words is not only very wide, but unwarranted. The words “permits or requires” in my view are used in s. 3 in the context of being authorised by law, or required by law and this to me seems all the more so because of the provisions contained in s. 165 of the Evidence Ordinance which empower a Judge to ask any question he pleases in any form at any time of any witness or party about any fact relevant or irrelevant. Considering the definition of evidence as embodied in s. 3 of the Evidence Ordinance, I am of the view that evidence signifies only the instruments by means of which relevant facts are brought before the Court by witnesses and documents. Evidence properly admitted is thus admissible for all purposes”. Mudie J in the case of *Kurup v PP* [1934] MLJ 17, 19 (HC) states “The definition of “Evidence” and “Court” in s. 3 of the Evidence Ordinance shows that evidence is the testimony of witnesses in a Court or before a person legally authorised to take evidence.”. Can also refer to the case of *Lee Kong Yin v PP* [1971] 2 MLJ 205 (HC). How about the evidential status of the unsworn statement from the dock? According to the case of *Muhd Haslam Abdullah v PP* [2020] 4 CLJ 328 where it was reported that “Without going into the matter in any detail, it suffices for us to say that there is a conflict among the High Courts as to whether an unsworn statement from the dock is evidence. *Wong Heng Fatt v Public Prosecutor* [1958] 1 LNS 96; [1959] MLJ 20, *Public Prosecutor v Sanassi* [1970] 1 LNS 118; [1970] 2 MLJ 198, and *Low Thim Fatt v Public Prosecutor* [1988] 1 LNS 218; [1989] 1 MLJ 304 say that it is not evidence. By contrast, *Chang Min Tat J in Ng Hoi Cheu v Public Prosecutor* [1967] 1 LNS 113; [1968] 1 MLJ 53 held that it is evidence. And there are dicta in many other cases, Malaysian, Australian and at least one decided by the Privy Council which say quite emphatically that such an unsworn statement is evidence for the purposes of a trial. All the relevant cases may be found in two articles published in the Malayan Law Journal. The first is that by that very learned scholar Prof Ahmad Ibrahim in [1975] 2 MLJ vi. The other is by Professor Mohd Akram in [2003] 1 MLJ clxix...”.

If we observed closely, Section 3 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] use the word “includes” when defining evidence. The significant of the word “includes” which been provided by the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] has also be discussed by the court. According to the case of *Chin Seow Noi v PP* [1994] 1 SLR 135 where Yong Pung How CJ said at page 156 “The use of the single word 'includes' in our s. 3 is clearly intended to make the definition of ‘evidence’ an extensive one: Within the context of our Evidence Act, ‘evidence’ may thus be given not just the narrow statutory meaning explicitly spelt out in section 3 itself but also, where applicable, its ordinary, popular and natural meaning”. In other words, the scope of admissible evidence as provided for in our Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] is considerably broader than that provided for in the Indian equivalent namely the Indian Evidence Act, 1872. Reference can be made to the case of *Dilworth & Ors v Commissioner of Stamps*, [1899] AC 99, [1895-99] All ER Rep Ext 1576, *Corporation of Portsmouth v Smith & Ors*. (1883) 13 QBD 184, *Lee Yuan Kwang & Ors v PP* [1995] 2 SLR 349 and *Noliana Bte Sulaiman v PP*

[2000] 4 MLJ 752. In *Noliana Bte Sulaiman v PP* [2000] 4 MLJ 752 Augustine Paul J states that: "This construction places the meaning of "evidence: in its proper perspective as it is capable of bringing within its sphere many matters which would otherwise fail to qualify. Thus, an unsworn statement made by an accused from the dock, being a matter before the court for consideration, will be "evidence" contrary to what has been held in *PP v. Sanassi* [1970] 1 LNS 118; [1970] 2 MLJ 198 and *Lee Kong Yin v PP* [1969] 1 LNS 85; [1970] 2 MLJ 205. Similarly, the confession of a co-accused is entitled to due consideration like any other evidence that has been proved unlike its treatment in the Indian courts in view of their narrow definition of the word "evidence". Further reference can also be made to the case of *Abdul Rashid & Anor v PP* [1994] 1 SLR 119, *PP v Rozmaan bin Jusoh & Anor* [1999] 2 SLR 181, *PP v Teong Lung Chiong* [2010] 1 LNS 45 and *Norshah Abdull Hamid & Others v Seloga Engineering Sdn Bhd* [2011] 2 LNS 0503.

3.2 Relevancy of Evidence

Relevant means, with regards to evidence, having some value or tendency to prove a matter of fact significant to the case. According to the United States of America Federal Rule of Evidence 401 states that "evidence is relevant if: (a) it has any tendency to make a fact more or less probable than it would be without the evidence; and (b) the fact is of consequence in determining the action." Generally, relevant evidence is admissible, and a common objection to the admission of evidence is that it is irrelevant. An example of relevant evidence in a murder trial could be the DNA evidence that defendant possessed the murder weapon and testimony from a witness who saw him at the scene around the time of the murder. (Legal Information Institute, 2024). The Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] also emphasize the need to submit relevant evidence. Section 5 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56] also lays down the rule that evidence may be given only of fact in issue and others facts declared by this Act to be relevant, and no other. Thus, it is very important for piece of evidence submitted to the court relevant to the case. The important of relevancy evidence has been strongly highlighted in many local cases. In *PP v Haji Kassim* (1971) 2 MLJ 115 it was stated that "If any fact is sought to be introduced in evidence it must be relevant and admissible under section 5". Chong Siew Fai CJ in *Thavanathan a/l Subramaniam v PP* [1997] 2 MLJ 401 at page 409 stated that "Of the law of evidence, the cardinal rule relating to relevancy is that subject to exclusionary rules, all evidence which sufficiently relevant to the facts in issue is admissible". Per Theisiger J in *R v Harz* [1966] 3 All ER 433, 449 stated that "The main general rule governing the entire subject is that evidence which is sufficiently relevant to an issue before the court is admissible and all that is irrelevant or insufficiently relevant should be exclude. Thus, the word relevant is to all intents and purposes synonymous with the phrase of probative value". Lord Simmon of Glaisdale in *DPP v Killbourne* [1973] AC 729 "Evidence is relevant if it is logically probative or disapprobative of some matter which requires proof". Per Lawton LJ in *R v Turner* [1975] 1 ALL ER 70 states "Relevance, however, does not result in evidence being admissible. It is a condition precedent to admissibility. Our law excludes evidence of many matters which in life outside the court sensible people take into consideration when making decisions. Two broad heads of exclusion are hearsay and opinion".

Section 5 must also be read with Section 165 of the Act where judge has the power to put questions about any fact relevant or irrelevant. Section 5 must also be read with Section 136 (1) of the Act where the court has power to accept or deny evidence based on relevancy. Per Augustine Paul J in *PP v Dato' Seri Anwar Bin Ibrahim* [1999] 2 MLJ 1, 170: "Questions of admissibility of Evidence are questions of law and are determinable by the judge. If it is the duty of the judge to admit all relevant evidence, it is no less his duty to exclude all irrelevant evidence. Section 5 declares that evidence may be given in any suit or proceeding of the existence or non-existence of every fact in issue and of such other facts as are hereinafter declared to be relevant, and of no others. Taylor J in *Muthusamy v PP* [1948] MLJ 57 stated that "It is the duty of the advocate to prepare his case with due regard to the real issues and with special care of law of evidence. If he cannot show that a proposed question is relevant he cannot complain if the magistrate promptly excludes it under section 5 which provides that "evidence may be given of legally relevant facts and no other". Further reference can be made to the case of *Oh Kien Sing v Wheels Electronics Manufacturing Sdn Bhd* [2022] 1 LNS 1287 and *Vasanta Amarasekara v PP* [2022] 4 CLJ 148.

3.3 Best Evidence Rule

The best evidence rule is a legal principle that holds an original piece of the evidence as the superior evidence. The rule specifies that secondary evidence, such as a copy or facsimile, will be not admissible if an original copy of the evidence exists and can be obtained. (Law.Com, 2024). This legal principle has its roots in 18th-century British law, at a time when copies would be rewritten by hand and hence more

vulnerable to inaccuracies. The best evidence rule is a common law rule of evidence which can be traced back at least as far as the 18th century. In the case of *Omychund v Barker* (1745) 1 Atk, 21, 49; 26 ER 15, 33, Lord Harwicke stated that “No evidence was admissible unless it was the best that the nature of the case will allow”. The general rule is that secondary evidence, such as a copy or facsimile, will not be admissible if an original document is available. Can refer further to the case of *R v Onufrejczyk* [1955] 1 AER 247, *Faridah Ariffin v Dr Lee Hock Bee & Another* [2006] 1 CLJ 660 and *Darahman Ibrahim & Others v Majlis Mesyuarat Kerajaan Negeri Perlis & Others* [2008] 4 CLJ 538. Reference can also be made to the case of *R v Quinn & Bloom* [1962] 2 QB 245. In this case, prosecution arose out of striptease performances alleged to have been conducted at the premises where the appellants carried on business as club proprietors. One of the exhibits (evidence) being submitted was a film which was a reconstruction of the striptease performance taken three months after the events complained of. The judge rejected the evidence. It was clear that in this case, the best evidence rule affected the admissibility of the evidence, which meant that if the best evidence was not available no other evidence was allowed to be given. However, the best evidence rule no longer has any effect on the “admissibility” of evidence. Lord Denning MR in *Garton v Hunter* [1969] 1 All ER 45 concerning the admissibility of secondary evidence of a document stated that “old rule has gone by the board long ago. The only remaining instance of it that I know is that if an original document is available in one’s hands, one must produce it. One cannot give secondary evidence by producing a copy. Nowadays we do not confine ourselves to the best evidence. We admit all relevant evidence. The goodness or badness of it goes only to weight, and not to admissibility”. Thus, the old rule where only best evidence will be admitted by the court is no longer applicable now. This means that the court now may admit the any other relevant evidence, as the good or bad will only affect the weight of the evidence rather than its admissibility in court. The change in the above approach was also reflected in the decision of *Kajala v Noble* (1982) 75 Cr App Rep 149. Further reference can also be made to the case of *Greenaway v Homelea Fittings (London) Ltd* [1985] WLR 234.

In Malaysia, the best evidence rule is still being reflected in several provisions under EA 1950 including Section 60 (1) (c) where oral evidence must be direct, Section 64 proof of documents by primary evidence, Section 91 where evidence of terms of contracts, grants, and other dispositions of property reduced to form of document. Several cases below explained the significance of the best evidence rule namely *Chow Siew Woh v PP* [1967] 1 MLJ 228, *Ho Chien v PP* [1936] 1 JLR 114, *Teoh Kee Keong v Tambun Mining Co Ltd* [1968] 1 MLJ 39 and *PP v Lim Kuan Hock* [1967] 2 MLJ 114. It is highly desirable for the interest of justice that in all cases, that the best evidence available & being presented in the court. Furthermore, the absence of the best evidence may always be the subject of adverse / bad comment by the judge and wild gossip from the audience. Subject to relevancy and the mode of proof therefore, evidence which is not consider as the best may still be admissible. In fact, by virtue of Section 136 of the Evidence Act 1950 [Act 56], the condition for admissibility of evidence is based on its relevancy to the case and not whether the evidence is the best evidence or not.

3.4 Burden and Standard of Proof

Every day, in courtrooms around the world, legal matters are being argued in front of judges and juries. In each case, the burden of proof and the standard of proof determine who has to prove what and to what extent. The term “Burden” and “standard” of proof are sometimes used interchangeably. In each case, one side has the “burden of proof”. Having this burden means the party must prove its case to the “trier of fact” the judge or jury, whoever is weighing the evidence. So, the party with the burden must produce evidence in support of their case. The standard of proof, on the other hand, refers to how convincing that evidence must be. (Ruth Maurice, 2024). In civil or criminal litigation, a burden of proof refers to the duty of the party to prove a fact or facts in issue. As per the principle of he who asserts must prove, therefore, the burden of proof can be found in Sections 101 and 102 in the Malaysian Evidence Act 1950 [act 56]. Section 101 emphasizes the legal burden of establishing a case. As stated in (1) whoever desires any court to give judgment as to any legal right or liability, dependent on the existence of facts which he asserts, must prove that those facts exist. Further, in (2) when a person is bound to prove the existence of any fact, it is said that the burden of proof lies on that person. In litigation, a standard of proof is the degree of proof required for any fact in issue, which means the party has to assess and establish the relevancy of evidence to the fact. As such, section 102 highlights the evidential burden of introducing evidence as it provides that the burden of proof in a suit or proceeding lies on that person who would fail if no evidence at all were given on either side. (Dr Claudia Lau, Dr Tan Swee Kiow and Mr Thamir Durai a/l Chelliah, 2020).

Tun Salleh Abas FCJ in *International Times v Leong Ho Yuen* [1980] 2 MLJ 86 (FC) states that “For the

purpose of this appeal it is necessary to bear in mind the distinction between the two senses in which the expressions burden of proof and onus of proof are used (See the case Nanji & Co. v Jatashankar Dossa & Ors. AIR 1961 SC 1474, 1478 and Raghavamma v Chenchamma AIR 1964 SC 136, 143) "The first sense, signified by the expression burden of proof such as referred to in s. 101 of the Evidence Act is the burden of establishing a case and this rests throughout the trial on the party who asserts the affirmative of the issue. The appellants in the present appeal relied on justification and fair comment. Therefore, the burden of proving these defences rests entirely upon them. The second sense referred to as onus of proof, on the other hand, relates to the responsibility of adducing evidence in order to discharge the burden of proof. The onus as opposed to burden is not stable and constantly shifts during the trial from one side to the other according to the scale of evidence and other preponderates. Such shifting is one continuous process in the evaluation of evidence. According to ss. 102 and 103 of the Evidence Act, if the party with whom this onus lies whether initially or subsequently as a result of its shifting does not give any or further evidence or gives evidence which is not sufficient, such party must fail. It is this onus that we are concerned with in the present appeal". Further reference can be made to the case of Kembang Serantau Sdn Bhd v Perbadanan Putrajaya [2022] 1 LNS 375, Hisham Tan Sri Halim v Teh Faridah Ahmad Norizan & Another [2021] 6 CLJ 56, Kerajaan Malaysia v Hanaz Sdn Bhd [2020] 1 LNS 1912 and EON Bank Bhd v Hotel Flamingo Sdn Bhd [2005] 1 MLJ 712.

In MGI Securities Sdn Bhd v Teong Teck Leng [2000] 5 CLJ 163, KL Rekhraj J states "In the face of this finding that the defence was without admissions; the onus of proof is now shifted to the plaintiff to prove its case; as ss. 101 and 102 of the Evidence Act 1950, requires "whosoever desire any court to give judgment as to any legal right or liability dependant on the existence of facts, which he exerts, must prove those facts do exist;" and here the plaintiff having chosen and elected not to lead the evidence of the oral agreements through its witnesses; the court could only hold that there was no evidence of the plaintiffs before the court to adjudicate upon; and accordingly dismissed the plaintiffs claim with costs". In Kam Pau Siong & Another v Wilayah Fabrication Sdn Bhd & Others [2004] 2 CLJ 816 it was states that "The law on the burden of proof is governed by the provisions found in Chapter VII of Part III of the Evidence Act 1950. In accordance with s. 101 of the Act, the legal burden of establishing that circumstances had arisen which would entitle SCC to appoint the receivers and managers, lie on SCC. We would agree with the contention of the plaintiff's counsel that up to now there is insufficient evidence to show that the debenture had crystallised. SCC would need to illustrate that the defendant had defaulted under the terms and conditions of the debenture. The burden of proof lies on SCC to show there was crystallization and that the receivers and managers were properly appointed. Since no such evidence is before us, we are of the view that the stand of SCC that the debenture had crystallised cannot stand at all".

4. CONCLUSION

It is very important for all the mentioned essential components for law of evidence which been discussed above be inserted in the course outlines for law of evidence subject. These essential components provide a basic understanding toward the principles, rules and regulations over the submission and admissibility of evidence in the court of law. At the same time, it is also very important for the facilitator of the subject make the necessary update over the matters which been discussed above. This is to ensure the all the principles, rules and regulations pertaining to law of evidence are in line with the current legal development. There might be changes been made towards the principles, rules and regulations either by the legislator or judiciary. Whatever it is, all these changes need to be highlighted to the students and be inserted into the course existing course outline provided by the law school.

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